

Project acronym: CS3MESH4EOSC

Deliverable D2.3: FULL IMPLEMENTATION OF QUALITY ASSURANCE AND MONITORING

Contractual delivery date	31-12-2021
Actual delivery date	07-03-2022
Grant Agreement no.	863353
Work Package	WP2
Nature of Deliverable	DEM (Demo)
Dissemination Level	PU (Public)
Lead Partner	SURFsara
Document ID	CS3MESH4EOSC-21-016
Authors	Daniel Müller, Holger Angenent, David Antoš, Milan Daneček, Renato Furter, Antoon Prins, Ron Trompert

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 863353

Versioning and Contributions History

Version	Date	Authors	Notes
0.1	24.11.2021	Ron Trompert (SURF)	Initial draft
0.2	06.12.2021	David Antoš (CESNET), Daniel Müller (WWU)	Comments incorporated
0.3	08.12.2021	David Antoš (CESNET)	Last feedback incorporated
0.4	04.03.2022	Ron Trompert (SURF)	Feedback from STC incorporated

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1 Introduction

The Science Mesh is designed to be a distributed federation of data storage and sharing services with very lightweight and minimalistic central services. The Science Mesh consists of several Sites running their own Enterprise File Sync and Share (EFSS) systems. Each of the Sites is expected to be financially sustainable by itself and each of them has their own policies and procedures related to user management, data handling, operations, and security. These sites, instead of operating as a disjoint collection of service islands, become nodes in a mesh of interconnected storage, applications and users. Despite them being independent, they are required to ensure minimal standards in the Science Mesh to ensure interoperability.

Interoperability between EFSS services is guaranteed by the Open Cloud Mesh (OCM¹) standard. To this “technical” coupling of nodes through the OCM standard, the Science Mesh will add agreed-upon policies and procedures with respect to operations and security, together with a governance structure. The goal is to create a coherent Infrastructure that can guarantee a service level having an adequate quality. Operational procedures to achieve this are described in deliverable D2.2² “Science Mesh service operational procedures” and the documents it references.

Having the procedures and policies available to achieve a certain level of quality assurance is one thing, but there has to be operational monitoring and alerting in place to support this. In this document, this will be described.

This deliverable is a demo. We came up with the following way to present our results to you: we will describe how the Quality Assurance infrastructure works and provide a description of various dashboards and what is shown in there. We will also provide links to our dashboards that are now operational so you can see them for yourself.

In this document, several acronyms are used. We will refrain from providing the definitions of them in this document but refer the reader to the Science Mesh Glossary³ for an explanation.

2 Architecture of the Science Mesh

In this section, a brief recapitulation of the Science Mesh’s architecture is given, as described in deliverable D2.1⁴. This provides some context which will be useful to understand the monitoring infrastructure that is discussed in this deliverable.

The Science Mesh consists of its participating Sites running EFSS services and a so-called Central Component. From a logical point of view, the Central Component is responsible for providing the few global services of the Science Mesh. However, it is by no means necessary that all those services run on a single node of the Science Mesh - they may be distributed across several Science Mesh partners. The interface between a Mesh node and the Mesh’s core operational infrastructure is what we call an

¹<https://github.com/cs3org/OCM-API>

²<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5602984>

³<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5038663>

⁴<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5602971>

Executive Module (EM).

Figure 1 below displays the conceptual architecture: The Central Component of the Science Mesh includes the monitoring and accounting infrastructure as well as the Central Database and Helpdesk. The monitoring infrastructure runs probes which return results to the monitoring infrastructure as to if the services running at the Sites are operational. Similarly, the accounting infrastructure collects usage metrics from Sites. The Central Database provides the EMs running within Sites with Science Mesh topology information.

Figure 1 Schematic overview of the Science Mesh architecture showing the information flows between the Central Component and the Sites

Topology information about the Science Mesh is contained in the Central Database. This includes Site names, endpoints, services running at the Sites and further meta-information. Executive Modules consume this information and use it to perform service and user discovery for the users (similar to the WAYF service in identity federations). Those discovery processes are the cornerstone of the Science Mesh, they serve to establish trust relationship between Users that are used for data sharing and application access. The Executive Modules also enforce sharing policies implemented at the Sites, i.e. which type of data sharing is permitted and what are the requirements to access applications.

Various functionalities of the Sites are periodically monitored. Accounting data is collected as well, containing gross aggregated usage statistics such as the number of shares and users, as well as the amount of storage used. None of the collected data can be traced back to an individual user.

The Science Mesh is a “share-nothing” infrastructure where all Sites can function independently of each other. They do not depend on the Central Component to provide basic functionality for the users. If the monitoring or accounting services go offline, the main service is not affected, and only monitoring/accounting operations will be stopped (graceful degradation). If the Central Database goes

offline, the EMs cannot be updated. While the information within the EMs may be stale, the EMs remain functional. Again, this is not critical as expected update intervals of the Science Mesh topology metadata are in days rather than minutes. Since the Central Database will be based on a relational database management system, it will be possible to opt for a geo-redundant solution with high availability, if it is deemed that downtime is not tolerable.

3 Quality Assurance

3.1 Detailed setup of the Central Component

While Figure 1 shows a schematic overview of the Science Mesh and its Central Component, Figure 2 shows more details about how the Central Component is implemented and its building blocks. In the sections below we will describe the purpose of these different building blocks.

Figure 2 The monitoring infrastructure of the Science Mesh

3.2 Central Database

As mentioned above, the Science Mesh has a central database in which all Science Mesh Sites are registered. This is the mesh metadata containing information about all sites and their respective services. Mesh metadata is used by the EMs at the various Sites to provide a service discovery mechanism for their users and, together with sharing policies configured locally in the Sites, they provide all necessary information for this task.

The technology we have chosen for this is called GOCdb⁵. GOCDB is a Configuration Management Database (CMDB) for recording and managing assets in e-

⁵<https://wiki.egi.eu/wiki/GOCDB>

infrastructure projects. It is used to define relevant topology objects including projects, groups, admin-domains, sites, services, service-groups, service-endpoints, service-downtimes, users and roles. The GOCdb software⁶ has been developed by EU-funded EGI projects and is now maintained by the EGI foundation⁷. It is open source and available under Apache-2.0 license. GOCDB allows us to store and manage Science Mesh topology information in a streamlined way. Currently, an on-premise version is used. For the interested reader, more information on the the software may be found online⁸.

Figure 3 shows the entry page of the Science Mesh GOCDB.

Figure 3 Screenshot of the GOCdb web I/F

The link to the Science Mesh GOCdb portal we have established may be found in Section **Error! Reference source not found.**

Still in Figure 3 you can find information about Sites, the services a Site offers, service endpoints, site contacts as well as down times (scheduled and unscheduled).

⁶<https://github.com/GOCDB>

⁷<https://www.egi.eu/about/egi-foundation/>

⁸https://wiki.egi.eu/w/images/d/d3/GOCDB5_Grid_Topology_Information_System.pdf

In order to access this portal, you first need to register. This is shown in Figure 4. There you find a registration page where you fill in your personal details such as your name, email address and Site affiliation. In the same form, you can also apply for a certain role in the GOCdb. The GOCdb distinguishes many different roles at Site level, NGI level, Project level and Service Group level. The roles supported are listed in the documentation⁹. From the rich possibilities implemented by GOCdb, just a small number of roles is important for Science Mesh operations. To explain them, we first need to briefly discuss the governance structure of the Science Mesh.

For a more detailed description of the governance structure of the Science Mesh and the role of the Operational Team, we refer to deliverable D2.2¹⁰ and particularly, the Science Mesh Policy Framework Constitution¹¹. The “Operational Team” plays an important role in Science Mesh operations and governance. The Operational Team is responsible for:

- Operations within the central Science Mesh infrastructure (e.g. Configuration Database, web site, etc.).
- Collaboration with the operators of member Sites.
- Reviewing and approving membership of new Sites.
- Receiving enquiries about the Science Mesh and forwarding them to the appropriate body.
- Processing applications to the Science Mesh and reviewing necessary technical aspects of them.
- Providing support to the Sites regarding operations and configuration of the Science Mesh and its services.
- Performing availability tests of the Sites (i.e., running tools to perform such tests), evaluating their Quality of Service, and handling security incidents regarding Science Mesh operations.

It follows we need to distinguish roles “Site admin” and “Operational Team member”. The Site admin can view and edit the details of his/her own Site. The “Operational team member” can suspend and unsuspend Sites. For reasons of scalability, the GOCdb has a managerial role for every Site called “Site Operations Manager”, which is able to manage the “Site admin” role for site admins at his/her own Site. The advantage of assigning that role is that changing the Site Admin role from one person to another can be handled locally and would not require submitting a ticket to the Science Mesh helpdesk.

For the Operational Team, the project-level GOCdb role “COD Staff”¹² would give them the necessary capabilities to perform their task.

⁹ https://wiki.egi.eu/wiki/GOCDB/Input_System_User_Documentation#Roles_definition

¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5602984>

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5040152>

¹² COD stands for “Central Operator on Duty” which stems from the Grid world and denotes people that perform the central monitoring tasks of the infrastructure.

Welcome to the ScienceMesh Account Registration!

Fill out the form below to register for a ScienceMesh account. A confirmation email will be sent to you shortly after registration.

<p>Email address: *</p> <input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>	<p>ScienceMesh Site: *</p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 2px;">SURFSARA SURFSARA ▼</div>
<p>Title: *</p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 2px;">Mr. ▼</div>	
<p>First name: *</p> <input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>	<p>Last name: *</p> <input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>
<p>Role: *</p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 2px;">Site administrator</div>	<p>Phone number:</p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 2px;">+49 030 123456</div>
<p>Password: *</p> <input style="width: 95%;" type="password"/>	<p>Confirm password: *</p> <input style="width: 95%;" type="password"/>

The password must fulfill the following criteria:

- Must be at least 8 characters long
- Must contain at least 1 lowercase letter
- Must contain at least 1 uppercase letter
- Must contain at least 1 digit

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

Already have an account? Login [here](#).

Figure 4 Screenshot of GOCdb registration page

In addition to these operational roles, the GOCdb also allows for roles in the security domain. There is a role for a central infrastructure-wide security officer and CSIRT officer, as well as for Site security officers. We expect them to be filled in at a later stage when the security policies and the Science Mesh security organisation is in place.

Add Site

NGI

Country

Timezone

Infrastructure

Certification Status

Domain * (Alphanumeric, dot dash and underscore)

Short Name * (Alphanumeric, dot dash and underscore)

Official Name (Alphanumeric and basic punctuation)

Home URL (http(s)://url_format)

GLIS URL (ldap://glis_url_format)

IP Range (a.b.c.d/e.f.g.h)

IPv6 Range (0000:0000:0000:0000:0000:0000:0000:0000/[int]) (optional [int] range)

Location (Alphanumeric and basic punctuation)

Latitude (-90 <= number <= 90)

Longitude (-180 <= number <= 180)

Description * (Alphanumeric and basic punctuation)

E-Mail * (valid email format)

Contact Telephone Number * (optional + at the start, numbers, dots spaces or dashes, multiple comma separated numbers allowed)

Emergency Telephone Number (optional + at the start, numbers, dots spaces or dashes, multiple comma separated numbers allowed)

Security Contact E-mail (CSIRT E-Mail) (valid email format)

Security Contact Telephone Number (CSIRT Telephone Number) (optional + at the start, numbers, dots spaces or dashes, multiple comma separated numbers allowed)

Alarm E-Mail (for LCG Tiers 1) (valid email format)

Helpdesk E-Mail (valid email format, multiple comma or semicolon separated addresses allowed)

Figure 5 The Site registration page of the GOCdb

Figure 5 shows the page for registering sites in the GOCdb. Apart from the obvious information like the name, URL etc., contact information is requested as well as security contact information and the email address of the Site’s helpdesk. This constitutes the Site’s metadata. When a Site has been added, then the Site admin is able to add services to the Site and declare downtimes of this service. This is shown in Figure 6 and 7, respectively. Two types of down times are distinguished here: “Outage” and “Warning” indicating that that a service is completely unavailable or just at risk of being unavailable, respectively.

Add Service

Hosting Site

Service Type

Service URL (Alphanumeric and \$-+!*(),;)

Host name * (valid FQDN format)

Host IP a.b.c.d

Host IPv6 (0000:0000:0000:0000:0000:0000:0000:0000[/int]) (optional [/int] range)

Host DN (/C=.../OU=.../...)

Description * (Alphanumeric and basic punctuation)

Host Operating System (Alphanumeric and basic punctuation)

Host Architecture (Alphanumeric and basic punctuation)

Is it a beta service (formerly PPS service?)

Is this service in production?

Is this service monitored?

Contact E-Mail * (valid email format) valid email format

Do you wish to receive notifications about this service?

Figure 6 Adding a service to a Site

Add Downtime

- To be SCHEDULED, start must be 24hrs in the future
- Time in UTC: **28/11/2021 15:56:09**

Severity:

Outage
Warning

Description:

You may need to update your site's timezone from UTC to the required value for your site - this version of GOCDDB uses a new timezone logic with new timezone labels taken from the 'Olsen' database. Where possible, the old values have been copied over, but some legacy values including those starting 'Etc/' are not supported and so UTC is specified by default.

Enter Times In: UTC Site Timezone

Starts on:

Ends on:

Select Affected Site

Figure 7 Declaring a downtime for a Site

3.3 Health Monitoring

To ensure overall high quality of service within the Science Mesh, all sites and their services must be constantly monitored and checked for their health status. The building blocks of the Central Component that take care of this are Prometheus¹³ and Blackbox Exporter¹⁴, Mentix¹⁵ and Alert Manager¹⁶. Prometheus is an open-source monitoring and alerting toolkit. It gathers health information and metrics from all Sites and their services and can be fully automated. Blackbox Exporter is an add-on for Prometheus that allows for the probing of endpoint over HTTP and other protocols. To interconnect all these different components, *Mentix* (short for Mesh Entity Exchanger) is used. Mentix is responsible for gathering site and service metadata from the GOCDDB and exporting it to the other services of the central component. This includes offering the site information via HTTP endpoints - which can then be consumed by other services which require information about the Science Mesh topology - as well as writing out target information used by Prometheus. Mentix can thus be seen as the bridge between the mesh topology information provider (i.e., GOCDDB) and all services that require this information. An overview of the general workflow of Mentix can be seen in Figure 2.

¹³<https://prometheus.io/>

¹⁴https://github.com/prometheus/blackbox_exporter

¹⁵<https://reva.link/docs/config/http/services/mentix/>

¹⁶<https://prometheus.io/docs/alerting/latest/alertmanager/>

As can be seen in Figure 2, the central Prometheus instance is automatically configured by Mentix: Whenever the Science Mesh topology has been modified, all targets which are to be monitored are updated as well.

Another major service of the central component is the Blackbox Exporter which also runs in the Central Component and is, just like Prometheus, automatically configured by Mentix. The Blackbox Exporter periodically runs various so-called *probes* for every service which check them for proper functionality and expose the results in the form of metrics consumable by Prometheus. This information is in return used to calculate overall site status, which is a combination of individual probe results, as well as an *availability* rating (i.e., the relative time of a site being in a healthy state).

Prometheus can also be used to notify Site administrators about any service issues reported through the health check probes. This also includes alerts about sites going from a healthy status into either warning or even critical state, ensuring that Site administrators can react swiftly to any arising problems. This task is performed by the Alert Manager that sends out email notifications to Sites in case of problems. It handles all alerts raised by Prometheus. It's connected to the site accounts service running on our Central Component. Registered Site admins can enable email alerts in their accounts to receive notifications about alerts from their site.

3.4 Metrics

Additionally, metrics like the total number of users, must be gathered and presented in a consumable way to get an overview of the mesh in its entirety. Sites may operate various EFSS solutions, so it is not feasible to come up with a generic solution for all systems. Therefore, we have chosen the approach to setup an HTTP-based service, using the IOP¹⁷ middleware, that reads data from a file which in turn needs to be put in place by a script periodically running at a site. The HTTP service exposes the metrics data to the Prometheus service, which queries it at regular intervals. It is up to the Site to write this script extracting information from its EFSS.

Currently, only the number of users is published but this can be easily extended with more. In the future it can be extended with the amount of storage in use or the number of shares, or even the number of shares across EFSS sites, and so on.

¹⁷<https://reva.link/>

The screenshot in Figure 8 shows an example of the data collected by Prometheus.

The screenshot shows the Prometheus web interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Prometheus', 'Alerts', 'Graph', 'Status', and 'Help'. Below this, there is a search bar containing the query 'revad_cs3_org_sciencemesh_site_total_num_users'. To the right of the search bar, there are statistics: 'Load time: 134ms', 'Resolution: 14s', and 'Total time series: 5'. Below the search bar, there is an 'Execute' button and a dropdown menu with '- insert metric at cursor -'. To the right of the dropdown, there is a 'Remove Graph' link. Below the search bar, there are two tabs: 'Graph' and 'Console'. The 'Graph' tab is active, and it shows a table of results. The table has two columns: 'Element' and 'Value'. The table contains five rows of data, each representing a different site. The last row is highlighted in grey.

Element	Value
revad_cs3_org_sciencemesh_site_total_num_users{country="CH",instance="sciencemesh.cernbox.cern.ch:443",job="sciencemesh-metrics",service_type="REVAD",site="CERN",site_id="home.cern::[CERN]",site_type="sciencemesh"}	12599
revad_cs3_org_sciencemesh_site_total_num_users{country="CZ",instance="sciencemesh.cesnet.cz:443",job="sciencemesh-metrics",service_type="REVAD",site="CESNET",site_id="www.cesnet.cz::[CESNET]",site_type="sciencemesh"}	328
revad_cs3_org_sciencemesh_site_total_num_users{country="DE",instance="sciencemesh-test.uni-muenster.de:443",job="sciencemesh-metrics",service_type="REVAD",site="WWU",site_id="www.uni-muenster.de::[WWU]",site_type="sciencemesh"}	3224
revad_cs3_org_sciencemesh_site_total_num_users{country="IT",instance="sciencemesh.cubbit.io:443",job="sciencemesh-metrics",service_type="REVAD",site="CUBBIT",site_id="www.cubbit.io::[CUBBIT]",site_type="sciencemesh"}	26596
revad_cs3_org_sciencemesh_site_total_num_users{country="PL",instance="sciencemesh.softwaremind.com:443",job="sciencemesh-metrics",service_type="REVAD",site="AILLERON",site_id="softwaremind.com::[AILLERON]",site_type="sciencemesh"}	18781

Figure 8 Screenshot Prometheus

3.5 Dashboard

All this rather technical information discussed in the sections above is presented to the user through various Grafana dashboards. In the first of the following screenshots, a collection of different metrics can be seen. The screenshot in Figure 10 shows a simple site health status overview.

Figure 9 Overview of the Science Mesh with its Sites and their number of Users

Health status		
Site ^	Country	Status
AILLERON	PL	Healthy
CERN	CH	Healthy
CESNET	CZ	Healthy
CUBBIT	IT	Healthy
SURFSARA	NL	Critical
SWITCH	CH	Warning
WWU	DE	Healthy

Figure 10 Science Mesh health monitoring

3.6 Links

Below you will find a series of links related to the building blocks of the central component. Note that, apart from the Grafana dashboard, no endpoints listed below are publicly accessible. We list them here in order to show the work that has been done. Furthermore, these links below represent the

current state of affairs but that may be subject to change in the future.

Building block	URL
GOCdb	https://gocdb.sciencemesh.uni-muenster.de/gocdb/login/
Prometheus	https://prometheus.sciencemesh.uni-muenster.de
Blackbox Exporter	https://bbe.sciencemesh.uni-muenster.de
Alert Manager	https://alerts.sciencemesh.uni-muenster.de
Grafana	https://grafana.sciencemesh.uni-muenster.de

Table 1 Links to the various Central Component building blocks

4 Concluding remarks

In this document a description has been given of the setup of the Central Component of the Science Mesh. The various building blocks of this Central Component have been described as well as the role they play in quality assurance and monitoring. The current setup will allow us to move to production with the Science Mesh.

At the time of writing, the Science Mesh is still in a testbed state. Entering production will probably show some hurdles that we need to overcome, also with respect to quality assurance and monitoring. The next steps to undertake are to assign the GOCdb “Site Admin” roles to people involved with the current testbed sites and form the “Operational Team”. The published metrics are rather limited at the moment. Adding additional metrics to the dashboard, like the amount of data stored, apps usage, number of shares and number of shares across EFSS Sites, are the most obvious one that are on the horizon.